

Performance of the Indian Tourism and Hospitality Stocks during the 2019-nCoV Outbreak - An Event Study using Stocks Listed on the NSE

Dr. Dharen Kumar Pandey¹ & Smt. Vineeta Kumari²

ABSTRACT

With a sample of 25 NSE listed stocks of the Indian tourism and hospitality industry using the event study methodology the hypothesis that “the 2019-nCoV outbreak had no impact on the stock prices of the tourism and hospitality industry” has been tested. The study evidence that the average abnormal returns (AARs), cumulative average abnormal returns (CAARs) and cumulative abnormal returns (CARs) are negative and significant for the long and the shorter event windows inferring that the global pandemic has significantly impacted the performance of the stocks of the Indian tourism and hospitality industry.

Keywords: Event study, abnormal returns, market model, global pandemic.

Introduction

The 2019-nCoV outbreak was not an anticipated one. Had it been so, it could not have done much harm to the society and the economy. Great economies failed to sustain its ill effects. Being a disease of easy human transmission, it taught the world the lessons of good hygiene and social distancing. People were forced to remain in their houses. A long holiday, indeed but no tour plan. The anticipated incomes of the tourism and hospitality industry went in vain. Almost all the industries have been worst hit but this industry will remain affected for time till the outbreak is permanently contained. Not only domestic but also international tourism has been hit hard. Be it a pilgrim or season’s celebration, a birthday, or an anniversary, the people were forced to celebrate it at home. Previous outbreaks including the SARS have affected a certain portion of the world but the 2019-nCoV outbreak has affected the whole world. The impact on a certain industry could be assessed by the performance of the stocks of that particular industry. The value of the stocks expressed in terms of the returns provides a basis for the interpretation of the degree of impact on that industry. We move forward to record the evidence of the outbreak affecting the returns of the tourism and hospitality industry using the event study methodology.

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1. (Corresponding author) Assistant Professor, P.G. Department of Commerce, Magadh University, Bodh Gaya, Bihar, India-824234 Email: dharenp@gmail.com Mobile: 8170080042
 2. Assistant Professor, P.G. Department of Commerce, Magadh University, Bodh Gaya, Bihar, India-824234 Email: vidhatamu@gmail.com Mobile: 8709744046

Pandey & Kumari (2020) discussed some literature relevant to event study methodologies in their unpublished paper wherein they studied the impact of the 2019-nCoV outbreak on the stock markets in the developed and emerging nations. They found that the studies conducted by Dimson (1979), Brown & Warner (1980 & 1985), Dyckman, et. al. (1984), Corrado (1989), Boehmer, et. al. (1991), Cowan (1992), Corrado&Zivney (1992), Campbell & Wasley (1993), Park (2004), Kolari & Pynnonen (2010 & 2011), Luoma&Pynnonen (2010), Ataullah, Song & Tippett (2011), Luoma (2011) and Dutta (2014) deals with the event study methodologies while providing evidence of best parametric and non-parametric test statistics. The review of the above literature provides the basis for conducting this event study. We review only the literature relevant to this study. A few numbers of researches have been conducted to study how such outbreaks affect the tourism and hospitality industry. Henderson & Ng (2004) conducted a study on the impacts of SARS on the hotel industry in Singapore and how managements react to it. They conclude that disasters are inevitable and will continue to occur but the world needs to be prepared. Pine & McKercher (2004) studied the impact of SARS on the tourism industry in Hong Kong and concluded that the tourism industry around the world has been badly hit by way of a decrease in personal and business travels as well as a reduction in capital investments. Chen, Jang & Kim (2007) used the event study method to study the impacts of SARS on the performance of the Taiwanese hotel stocks and found significant negative cumulative abnormal returns on and around the SARS outbreak. Chen, et. al. (2009) studied the impacts of SARS on the Taiwanese industries using the event study method with the GARCH process and concluded that the outbreak had negatively impacted the tourism, retail and wholesale industry. Min, Lim & Kung (2010) analyzed the impacts of SARS on Japanese inbound tourism using an intervention model with SARIMA to conclude that Japanese inbound tourism has been worst hit by the SARS outbreak during the first 5 months. Donadelli, Kizys & Riedel (2017) collected the data of 102 NYSE listed pharmaceutical companies during dangerous disease outbreaks and studied the impact on investor's behavior to conclude that "although the disease spread is bad news for the mainstream, some of the market traders make it a good news using profitable trading strategies to get significant positive returns". Kim et. al. (2020) examined how the food-related epidemics impacted the financial performance of restaurants using the event study method to conclude that the epidemics have a negative impact on the restaurant industry.

Although a few studies are available in respect of impacts of disease outbreaks on the tourism and hospitality industry, they claim that such outbreaks negatively impact this industry. The studies are focused on the impacts of the SARS on the Asian tourism industry because only a few nations were affected by the outbreak. However, unexpectedly the 2019-nCoV outbreak has spread all over the world forcing the workforce and development mechanisms to pause. Not only tourism and hospitality but almost every industry has been hit by the outbreak. A series of lockdowns and travel restrictions have impacted the tourism and hospitality industry but to trace the abnormality of such impacts, statistical inferences are necessary. A timely study on the impacts of 2019-nCoV outbreak will not only provide the actual impact on the stocks of this industry but also help management to plan for future unexpected outbreaks. An event study is anticipated to add to the literature of tourism as well as finance.

Objectives and Research Methodology

Objectives of the study: The study aims to examine the impacts of the 2019-nCoV outbreak on the performance of the stocks of the tourism and hospitality industry in India. The null hypothesis that

“the 2019-nCoV outbreak had no impact on the stock prices of the tourism and hospitality industry” will be tested to conclude whether or not the outbreak has impacted the performance of the Indian tourism and hospitality industry stocks.

Sample construction: The initial sample for the study consisted of 29 stocks from the tourism, hospitality, and tourism finance. Out of these, two companies were not listed on the NSE and sufficient data was not available for two other companies which were listed just a few months before the event. The final sample consisted of 25 stocks from the tourism and hospitality industry. The list of sample stocks is provided in table 1.

Table: List of Sample Stocks

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Sl. No.	Name	NSE Code
1	India Tourism Development Corporation Ltd	ITDC
2	Tourism Finance Corporation India Ltd	TFCILTD
3	Cox & Kings Ltd	COX&KINGS
4	Thomas Cook (India)Ltd	THOMASCOOK
5	BLS International Services Ltd	BLS
6	Wonderla Holidays Ltd	WONDERLA
7	Country Club Hospitality & Holidays Ltd	CCHHL
8	Mahindra Holidays & Resorts India Ltd	MHRIL
9	The Byke Hospitality Ltd	BYKE
10	Taj GVK Hotels & Resorts Ltd	TAJGVK
11	EIH Associated Hotels Limited	EIHAHOTELS
12	Lemon Tree Hotels Ltd	LEMONTREE
13	Asian Hotels (EAST) Ltd	AHLEAST
14	Asian Hotels (WEST) Ltd	AHLWEST
15	TGB Banquets & Hotels Ltd	TGBHOTELS
16	EIH Ltd	EIHOTEL
17	Kamat Hotels (I) Ltd	KAMATHOTEL
18	Chalet Hotels Ltd	CHALET
19	Apollo Sindoori Hotels Ltd	APOLSINHOT
20	Viceroy Hotels Ltd	VICEROY
21	Asian Hotels (NORTH) Ltd	ASIANHOTNR
22	Royal Orchid Hotels Ltd	ROHLTD
23	The India Hotels Company Ltd	INDHOTEL
24	Advani Hotels & Resorts (India) Ltd	ADVANIHOTR
25	Oriental Hotels Ltd	ORIENTHOT

Event Date and Estimation Period: The event for this study is the declaration made by the WHO on 11th March, 2020. The WHO declared the 2019-nCoV outbreak as a global pandemic on this date. Hence, this is the event for our study. The effective date of the announcement has been adjusted to 12th March 2020 because, by the time the declaration was made on 11th March 2020, the Indian stock market was already closed. So the event date (t) is 12th March, 2020 for our study. The event window begins from (t-30)th day and ends on (t+30)th day. A 120-days estimation window has been taken for this study. A pictorial view of the event timeline is provided in figure 1.

Figure 1: Timeline of the event

Estimation of normal returns: The estimation of normal returns is very essential for calculating abnormal returns. The normal return may be defined as such return which would have been yielded if the event had not occurred. There are many methods available for the estimation of normal returns. Dyckman, Philbrick & Stephan (1984) recommend the Ordinary Least Squares market model for better results. Hence, the normal returns are estimated using the Ordinary Least Squares market model. For the market return we chose NIFTY. The normal return is estimated with the following equation:

$$ER_{st} = \alpha + \beta R_{mt} \dots \dots \dots eq. (i)$$

Where,

ER_{st} is the estimated normal return of the stock s on day t.

α & β are intercept and slope coefficients of the OLS model

R_{mt} is the benchmark return (NIFTY) on day t.

The alpha and beta coefficient are calculated from the regression of the data available for the 120 days from t₋₁₅₀ to t₋₃₁.

Daily abnormal returns: The daily abnormal return refers to the abnormal behavior of the stock returns as compared to the market reaction. It is assumed that the stocks should behave similar to the market based on its previous beta values. Any abnormal fluctuations mean the presence of abnormality. The daily returns are required to be calculated first. We use the log returns for this purpose. The daily log returns are calculated with the help of MS-excel. The daily abnormal return is calculated as below:

$$AR_{st} = R_{st} - ER_{st} \dots \dots \dots eq. (ii)$$

Where,

AR_{st} is the abnormal return on stock s on day t;

ER_{st} is the normal return as per eq. (i) above, and,

R_{st} is the actual return (log returns) on stock s on day t.

Average and cumulative average abnormal returns: We aggregate the abnormal returns of each sample stocks on each of the days in the event window to arrive at the total abnormal return for each day. The same is then divided by the sample size (N) to get the average abnormal return. The following equation is used for calculating the average abnormal return:

$$AAR_t = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{s=1}^N AR_{st} \dots \dots \dots eq. (iii)$$

Where,

AAR_t denotes the average abnormal return on day t, and,

N is the number of stocks.

These AARs becomes the basis for calculating the cumulative AARs for the event window.

Test for significance: The calculated AARs and the CAARs need to be tested for their significance to accept or reject the null hypothesis. We use the test-statistics used by Brown & Warner (1980 & 1985). For this purpose, the standard deviation of the AARs for the estimation window of each of the stocks is calculated and the same is aggregated for the entire sample. The aggregated estimation window standard deviation is arrived as follows:

$$\sigma_{N,e} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{s=1}^N \sigma_{s,e}^2}{N}} \dots \dots \dots eq. (iv)$$

Where, $\sigma_{s,e}$ is the estimation window standard deviation for stock s.

Once the aggregate estimation window standard deviation is calculated, the t-statistics are calculated as below:

$$t_{AARt} = \frac{AAR_t}{\sigma_{N,e}} \dots \dots \dots eq. (v)$$

Similarly, the t-statistics for CAARs is calculated as:

$$t_{CAARt} = \frac{CAAR_t}{\sigma_{N,e} \sqrt{N_{t+1}}} \dots \dots \dots eq. (vi)$$

Where,

t_{AAR_t} and t_{CAAR_t} are the test statistics for AARs and CAARs on day t

N_{t+1} denotes the absolute value (ignores the -ve sign) of event day t plus 1

Further, we use the Corradorank test statistic, a non-parametric test, developed by Corrado (1989) as modified by Ataullah, Song & Tippet (2011). The simplified equation is as below:

$$t_{Corrado} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{N(T^2-1)}} \sum_{s=1}^n [2K(AR_{st}) - (T - 1)] \dots\dots\dots eq.(vii)$$

Where,

N is the sample size

T is the total number of ARs for the stock(in our case, it is 181)

$K(AR_{st})$ is the rank of the AR of the stock s in the 181 days

We also use the Ataullah, Song & Tippet (2011) modified Corrado equation for measuring the t-statistics for the CARs of shorter event windows as below:

$$t_{Cor(modified)} = \sqrt{\frac{3}{M(T+1)(T-M)}} \sum_{s=1}^n [2K(CAR_{stM}) - M(T + 1)] \dots\dots\dots eq.(viii)$$

Where,

$K(CAR_{stM})$ is the sum of the $K(AR_{st})$ for the period M

M is the no of days in the Event Window

Interpreting the empirical results: We use the calculated test statistics for interpreting the significant impact on the stock performance. The significance is tested at 1% and 5%. If the critical value of the test statistics is higher than the calculated value (absolute value), the abnormal returns are not significant. The critical values for a degree of freedom of 24 for the sample size 25 are 2.797 and 2.063 at 1% and 5% level respectively. Further, if the abnormal returns are negative and the respective test statistics are significant, it may indicate that the performance of the stocks is negatively and significantly impacted by the event.

Quantitative Analysis

This section covers the analysis of the sample data obtained from the NSE website for the study period. A total of 4525 observations of daily returns across 25 stocks are available for analysis. Dyckman, Philbrick & Stephan (1984) compared various event study methodologies and concluded that abnormal data do not have any effect on the conclusions made on the basis of the t-test. Their results are congruent with Brown & Warner (1984). So we do not test the normality of the data and proceed towards data analysis. The data has been processed in the MS-excel for calculating the AARs, CAARs, and the test statistics.

The AARs and CAARs for the entire event window of 61 days are presented in table 2. It can be seen that a total of 24 negative AARs are present in the pre-event day window while only 14 negative

AARs are present in the post-event day window. The AAR on the event day is also negative. The AARs are negative throughout the period t-11 to t+1. Negative CAARs are noticed on all the days during the event window except on t-21. The presence of negative AARs and CAARs indicate some abnormality in the daily returns of the stocks in the Indian tourism and hospitality industry.

Table 2: AARs and CAARs during the event window

Days	AARs	CAARs	Days	AARs	CAARs
t-30	-0.005	-0.005	t	-0.032	-0.185
t-29	-0.005	-0.010	t+1	-0.041	-0.226
t-28	-0.001	-0.011	t+2	0.007	-0.219
t-27	-0.007	-0.019	t+3	-0.016	-0.235
t-26	-0.014	-0.033	t+4	-0.014	-0.249
t-25	-0.002	-0.035	t+5	-0.035	-0.284
t-24	0.001	-0.034	t+6	-0.003	-0.287
t-23	0.006	-0.027	t+7	0.002	-0.286
t-22	0.009	-0.018	t+8	-0.020	-0.305
t-21	0.026	0.008	t+9	-0.035	-0.340
t-20	-0.013	-0.005	t+10	0.009	-0.331
t-19	-0.021	-0.025	t+11	0.010	-0.321
t-18	-0.009	-0.035	t+12	0.003	-0.318
t-17	-0.003	-0.038	t+13	0.003	-0.315
t-16	-0.003	-0.040	t+14	0.038	-0.277
t-15	-0.009	-0.049	t+15	0.014	-0.264
t-14	-0.006	-0.055	t+16	-0.045	-0.308
t-13	0.018	-0.038	t+17	0.034	-0.275
t-12	0.008	-0.029	t+18	-0.002	-0.276
t-11	-0.009	-0.038	t+19	0.018	-0.259
t-10	-0.009	-0.047	t+20	0.027	-0.232
t-9	-0.014	-0.061	t+21	0.012	-0.220
t-8	-0.013	-0.074	t+22	0.005	-0.216
t-7	-0.011	-0.085	t+23	0.008	-0.208
t-6	-0.007	-0.092	t+24	0.007	-0.201
t-5	-0.023	-0.115	t+25	-0.013	-0.213
t-4	-0.010	-0.125	t+26	0.021	-0.193
t-3	-0.010	-0.135	t+27	-0.021	-0.214
t-2	-0.010	-0.145	t+28	-0.022	-0.237
t-1	-0.007	-0.152	t+29	-0.007	-0.244
T	-0.032	-0.185	t+30	-0.006	-0.250

Source: Author’s calculation in MS-excel

The graphical representation of these AARs and CAARs has been provided in figure2. The trend of CAARs is seen moving steeply downwards from the (t-12)th day with a recovery on (t+12)th day but again a sharp downward trend from (t+26)th day. The R² value of the trend-line is 0.98 which indicates that it almost accurately predicts the trend of the CAARs. The trend shows negative CAARs for the entire event window period indicating that the performance of the stocks of the Indian tourism and hospitality industry has been negatively impacted. However, this negative impact must be tested for significance.

Figure 2: AARs and CAARs in the event window

Source: Based on the author’s calculation in MS-excel

The analysis of the AARs and CAARs indicated a negative impact but its significance is yet to be tested. Table 3 presents the test statistics (as in Brown & Warner, 1980 & 1985) and the Corrado test statistics for all the days through the event window. During the pre-event day period 6 AARs (3 each at 1% and 5% level) and 10 CAARs (2 at 5% level and 8 at 1% level) are found significant. During the post-event day period 15 AARs (4 at 5% level and 11 at 1% level) are significant while all the CAARs (3 at 5% level and 27 at 1% level) are significant for this period. The event day AAR and CAAR are also significant at a 1% level. The table also depicts that 2 pre-event day AARs and 6 post-event day AARs are positive as well as significant. The Corrado test statistics indicate 5 significant CARs (2 at 5% level and 3 at 1% level) in the pre-event day period and 10 significant CARs (all at 1% level) in the post-event day period. The Corrado test statistics indicate significant CAR at a 5% level on the event day also. The negative and significant CAARs through the days t-10 to t+30 indicate that the 2019-nCoV outbreak being declared as a global pandemic has negatively impact the performance of the stocks of the Indian tourism and hospitality industry. The results are similar to Chen, Jang & Kim (2007), and Chen, et. al.(2009).

Table 3: Test statistics for all the days during the event window period

Days	t _{AAR}	t _{CAAR}	t _{Corrado}	Days	t _{AAR}	t _{CAAR}	t _{Corrado}
t-30	-0.828	-0.149	0.815	t	-4.998**	-28.582**	2.147*
t-29	-0.737	-0.286	0.869	t+1	-6.415**	-24.746**	2.986**
t-28	-0.209	-0.330	-0.299	t+2	1.034	-19.608**	-0.295
t-27	-1.092	-0.542	1.179	t+3	-2.423*	-18.193**	1.225
t-26	-2.216*	-0.978	2.622*	t+4	-2.213*	-17.262**	1.053
t-25	-0.266	-1.049	1.171	t+5	-5.389**	-17.958**	4.134**
t-24	0.145	-1.041	0.191	t+6	-0.479	-16.807**	0.279
t-23	0.987	-0.861	-1.424	t+7	0.267	-15.627**	0.456
t-22	1.413	-0.585	-0.662	t+8	-3.025**	-15.741**	1.478
t-21	4.098**	0.276	-1.822	t+9	-5.401**	-16.642**	2.729**
t-20	-2.012	-0.157	1.788	t+10	1.399	-15.446**	-0.348
t-19	-3.206**	-0.878	3.292**	t+11	1.596	-14.327**	-1.424
t-18	-1.419	-1.226	1.776	t+12	0.442	-13.643**	-1.210
t-17	-0.474	-1.371	0.528	t+13	0.389	-13.043**	0.586
t-16	-0.446	-1.519	0.777	t+14	5.887**	-11.080**	-4.195**
t-15	-1.378	-1.910	1.374	t+15	2.096*	-10.205**	-1.554
t-14	-0.907	-2.207	0.011	t+16	-6.896**	-11.573**	4.628**
t-13	2.732*	-1.555	-2.140*	t+17	5.224**	-10.015**	-4.272**
t-12	1.294	-1.254	-0.727	t+18	-0.255	-9.807**	1.060
t-11	-1.398	-1.709	0.945	t+19	2.717*	-8.951**	-1.405
t-10	-1.355	-2.194*	1.221	t+20	4.127**	-7.834**	-3.074**
t-9	-2.149*	-2.980**	3.016**	t+21	1.800	-7.270*	-0.643
t-8	-2.061	-3.829**	1.298	t+22	0.702	-6.964**	-1.060
t-7	-1.659	-4.647**	0.896	t+23	1.204	-6.572**	-1.221
t-6	-1.143	-5.400*	1.382	t+24	1.104	-6.218**	-0.272
t-5	-3.571**	-7.291**	3.816**	t+25	-1.945	-6.479**	2.033
t-4	-1.506	-8.660**	1.566	t+26	3.184**	-5.745*	-2.963**
t-3	-1.581	-10.473**	1.194	t+27	-3.310**	-6.267**	3.437**
t-2	-1.563	-12.996**	0.574	t+28	-3.475**	-6.803**	3.977**
t-1	-1.074	-16.676**	0.509	t+29	-1.095	-6.889**	1.631
t	-4.998**	-28.582**	2.147*	t+30	-0.945	-6.947*	1.876

*Significant at 5% level **Significant at 1% level

Source: Author's calculation in MS-excel

The analysis of the shorter event window periods may reflect results that may strongly evidence the inferences drawn by the event window period of 61 days. Table 4 presents the test statistics of AARs, CAARs, and Corrado (modified) test statistics for CARs around the event day. We have calculated these test statistics for -1 to +1, -3 to +3, and -7 to +7 event windows. It is noticed that the AARs, CAARs, and CARs for all the three shorter event windows are significant. Although the AARs for 15 days and 7 day's event window are found to be significant at a 5% level, the rest of the figures are significant at 1% level. The AARs and CAARs for all three event windows are negative. Negative and significant figures indicate that the event has significantly impacted the stock performance of the Indian tourism and hospitality industry and the impact is negative, too.

Table 4: AARs and CAARs around Event Day

Window Period	AAR	CAAR	t_{AAR}	t_{CAAR}	$t_{Cor(modified)}$
-7 to +7	-0.014	-0.211	-2.181*	-8.447**	27.74**
-3 to +3	-0.016	-0.110	-2.432*	-6.433**	14.744**
-1 to +1	-0.027	-0.081	-4.162**	-7.209**	-85.572**

*Significant at 5% level **Significant at 1% level

Source: Author's calculation in MS-excel

Conclusions

The analysis of the AARs, CAARs, and CARs for both longer (61 days) and the shorter (3 days, 7 days & 15 days) event windows reveal that the stocks of the Indian tourism and hospitality industry have been significantly impacted by the global pandemic. The news of the 2019-nCoV outbreak being declared as a global pandemic led to a series of lockdowns and travel restrictions all over the world creating a crisis for the tourism and hospitality industry. With no clear predictions about the end of this pandemic, the shareholders are uncertain about the revival of this industry-leading to low confidence in the stocks of the tourism and hospitality industry. The Brown & Warner (1980 & 1985) test statistic, Corrado rank test statistics, and the Ataullah, Song & Tippet (2011)-modified Corrado rank test statistics are statistically significant indicating the presence of significant AARs, CAARs and CARs during the event window. This study provides evidence that the 2019-nCoV outbreak being declared as a global pandemic has had a significant negative impact on the performance of the Indian tourism and hospitality industry stocks. The weak market sentiments as a result of the uncertainty regarding the revival have resulted in such performance.

Implications and Limitations of the Study

There is a lack of event study on the impacts of epidemics on the stocks of the Indian tourism and hospitality industry. Although a few event studies have been conducted in respect of the tourism and hospitality industry in the Asia region, they are a decade old. We anticipate that this study will add to the literature of the event study methodologies as well as the literature of tourism and hospitality discipline. The study will help the management understand the reactions of the shareholders/investors during such outbreaks. The study may possess some limitations as the normality of data has not been

assessed but the use of both parametric and non-parametric tests eliminates the misinterpretation of the significance. Further, we could not do an event study on the impacts of the outbreak on the global tourism industry. Hence, future research may be conducted to study the impact on the global tourism and hospitality industry as the outbreak has impacted the whole world.

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